

FORECASTING ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS CAUSED BY OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY OPERATIONS**Sheydai T.,**

*Master, Teaching assistant of the department Management,
Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry University,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0743-834X>*

Yatzyuk O.,

*Master, Director of the Sikorsky Challenge Startup School,
Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3943-7352>*

Bui Yu.,

*Assistant of the Department of Applied Economics,
Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0096-2384>*

Berezhnytska U.,

*Candidate of economic sciences,
Head of the Department of Applied Economics
Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5354-8502>*

Antonenko N.

*Candidate of technical sciences,
Ukrainian Engineering Pedagogics Academy
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5576-3388>*

Abstract

The territory of Azerbaijan, rich in underground and surface resources, is also rich in hydrocarbon resources. The development of hydrocarbon deposits in the Azerbaijani sector of the Caspian Sea, agreed upon in the "Contract of the Century", gave impetus to joint development with the world's leading oil companies and contributed to the development of oil and gas fields in Azerbaijan. The oil and gas complex has given a special impetus to both the economic and social development of Azerbaijan. One of the main tasks facing the Republic of Azerbaijan is to ensure the energy needs of the population, consolidate achievements in the successful development of the economy. In this article, we analyze the environmental and economic risks that arise both during the development and further oil processing of oil and gas fields. The purpose of the study is to develop proposals for more effective prevention of environmental risks on the example of some fields in Azerbaijan. The subject of the study is the fuel and energy complex of Azerbaijan and at the same time the issue of ensuring ecological balance. The proposed article is based on the study of some problems of harming the environment of some fields of Azerbaijan in order to minimize the impact on the environment.

Keywords: forecasting environmental pollution, oil and gas industry, environmental risks, pollution prevention.

Introduction

The development of the oil and gas complex in the world and in Azerbaijan has been the basis of the progress of society and the economy for many decades. Today, the development of energy has become one of the most successful and decisive directions of state policy in the Republic of Azerbaijan. The wealth of the oil and gas complex allows us to build a sovereign Azerbaijan, create a modern state. With all the available opportunities and potential sources of energy, Azerbaijan with a transitional economy is ahead of other countries in the same situation.

The rapid development of the oil and gas complex should not only meet the energy needs of the population, but also serve its well-being. The development of the oil and gas complex of Azerbaijan makes it possible to ensure sufficiently high rates of economic development, but at the same time creates a number of environmental problems in the state. Therefore, it is important to ensure the environmental safety of the oil and gas

complex, as well as the population's need for energy resources primarily through the development of renewable energy sources.

Since the oil and gas complex is closely connected with all spheres of life in Azerbaijan, its condition has a significant impact on the socio-economic policy of the state. Thus, the sharp drop in oil prices over the past year has significantly complicated the socio-economic situation in Azerbaijan as a whole. Therefore, the analysis of the current state of the leading sector of the Azerbaijani economy – the oil and gas complex as a whole, the identification of factors affecting its development, is an important and urgent task.

The purpose of the study is to develop proposals for more effective prevention of environmental risks on the example of oil and gas fields of Azerbaijan.

The subject of the study is the state of the oil and gas complex of Azerbaijan and at the same time the issue of ensuring ecological balance in its development.

The scientific novelty of the research consists in studying and grouping the strategy for the development

of the oil and gas complex in Azerbaijan, developing proposals for the effective use of energy sources and taking measures to prevent the impact of this use on the environment.

Literature review

The oil and gas complex, primarily the oil industry, plays an important role in socio-economic development, in mobilizing the entire economic potential of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It is no coincidence that the Azerbaijani state, pursuing an "open door" policy based on the principles of mutually beneficial cooperation, creates favourable conditions for the participation of foreign capital in the development of oil fields [1].

The study of issues related to this gas topic was reflected in the works of many researchers, after the Republic of Azerbaijan there is a significant potential for the development of the oil industry, which is the basic structure of the economy [2], official statistics [3] and other sources, the authors examined the problem as a whole and highlighted many aspects of the development of the oil industry. Describing the dynamics of the development of the oil industry of Azerbaijan, these authors, in addition to focusing on the activities of Western industrialists, also explained the activities of representatives of Russian capital, which has a large multinational structure [4].

Many works have been written both on environmental protection and on the effective use (forecasting) of natural resources [5]. In the works of M. D. Goldfein, N. V. Kozhevnikov, N. I. Kozhevnikova other researchers [6], forecasting methods and their basic principles are studied.

Information about the oil and gas complex of Azerbaijan was repeatedly emphasized in the writings of early medieval researchers and travelers [7] the first information about the extraction and distillation of Baku oil by wells was given in his writings by the Arab historian of the 13th century, Muhammad ibn Najib Bakran [8].

The rapidly developing oil and gas complex in the modern world is the basis for the development of key economic sectors and determines the progress of social production. To this end, the scientists conducted extensive studies of the economics of the oil and gas complex and reflected the results in their works. Research by Ukrainian and Azerbaijani scientists Vagif Gadirov, Oleksandr Menshov, Roman Kuderavets, Kamran Gadirov on structural forms, formation and destruction of oil and gas deposits, geographical location of the main oil and gas-bearing deposits of Ukraine and Azerbaijan showed that oil deposits, regardless of their structural form, in gravitational and geomagnetic fields are marked by local minima, and the intensity of local gravi-magnetic minima depends to a greater extent on the strength of the oil and gas reservoir than on its depth [9]. Rafiga Huseynzade, Azer Aliyev research the historical experience of the construction of main oil and gas pipelines and its environmental priorities for Azerbaijan. The experience of the above-mentioned country's oil and gas industry in exploration, production, processing and transportation was studied in the collections of works of authors who lived in the Middle Ages, in particular, the first oil well in the world was drilled

on the Absheron Peninsula in Azerbaijan in 1846 [10]. It is also worth noting that the oil industry of Azerbaijan has gone through various stages of decline and recovery during the entire period of development, but despite this, many oil and gas fields have been discovered and developed in the country. At the current stage of its development, the oil and gas industry accounts for about 90% of Azerbaijan's export revenues and about 60% of the country's state budget. The development of the oil and gas industry contributed to a significant increase in the standard of living in Azerbaijan since the late 1990s. Thus, Azerbaijani oil scientists have become famous not only in their own country, but also abroad for their practical and scientific activities.

R. N. Nuralieva the monograph "Economic and environmental problems of the development of the fuel and energy complex of Azerbaijan" shows the theoretical and methodological foundations of the relationship of the oil and gas industry with the environment, analyzes the environmental situation in the country, highlights the principles of environmental protection [11].

One of the important tasks facing the oil and gas complex of the Republic of Azerbaijan today is to better meet the needs of the economy and the population of the country in energy resources and consolidate the results achieved. To fulfill this important task, the "State Program for the Development of the Fuel and Energy Complex of the Republic of Azerbaijan" provides for the implementation of specific measures for their implementation in the next decade and defines the directions of development of territories [12, 13].

Results and discussion

In the next decade, due to the shortening of the life of oil and gas fields, the Azerbaijan State Oil Company (SOCAR) will face problems in the process of oil and gas production, as well as in the supply sector. This is considered a natural phenomenon, but, thus, a reduction in production in large and intensively developed territories over the course of a century will be inevitable. According to forecasts, in 2025, oil supplies to the country will be reduced to 6.9 million tons with an annual reduction of 1-2%. During this period, the country's population will increase by 22% from 10 million to 11 million in 2025 [14].

A stronger economy will increase investments in the social sector and improve people's well-being. A favourable social situation will be accompanied by an increase in energy demand. In such conditions, the number of cars in the country will double and in 2025 will average 2 million. Currently, the country needs 1.1 million tons of pure gasoline and 1.2 million tons of diesel fuel. It is expected that in 2025 the demand for gasoline will grow by 80%, and for diesel fuel – by 2 times. To meet this demand, SOCAR needs to increase production from the current 6 million tons to 9 million tons in 2025. This situation will affect the productivity of the oil and gas industry, and, accordingly, this process will affect the growth rate of GDP. In different development scenarios, this impact can be multifaceted: first of all, the decline in oil production by SOCAR will affect its capital intensity and foreign exchange earnings. As a result, the country's impact on economic growth in the oil sector will be limited. On the other

hand, the country's transport sector will suffer from this deficit, and it will have to create its own new supply system. Naturally, SOCAR will replace the loss of oil in GDP with an increase in gas production. However, the decline in oil production will affect gas production to some extent. In this context, it is important to note that natural gas currently dominates the global oil and gas complex. The world has entered a period of growth in natural gas consumption. It is sometimes called the "methane age" of modern human civilization.

It was noted that natural gas reserves in Azerbaijan have great potential. This optimistic scenario (with an increase in natural gas production) leads to another perspective: despite the growing gas potential of the republic, based on modern economic realities and environmental requirements, it is necessary to use it more effectively and create appropriate production structures in this direction. Based on the long-term goals of the Azerbaijan national oil strategy, at the next stage of development, it is necessary to use gas resources more efficiently and develop the gas chemical industry, especially when opening new gas and energy enterprises, increasing production capacities and creating new gas technologies.

According to the processing technology, 85-90% of the mixture of natural and associated gases is methane, used in everyday life and energy [15-19], the rest is ethane, propane, etc., which are valuable raw materials for gas chemistry. It is impossible to organize efficient processing at the Garadagh gas processing plant, which is operating at full capacity and does not meet modern technological and environmental requirements. Therefore, it is necessary to build new modern plants of such production capacity that would meet modern technological standards and volumes of gas produced in the country, as well as the creation of a gas chemical complex based on valuable components. The main problems of economic and environmental processes in the oil and gas complex consist in changes in the nature of the environment, determining the relationship between their social and production results, determining the scale, nature and trends of environmental change, identifying areas with a bad environment. Therefore, it is important to carry out economic and social assessments, and each assessment should have a certain value. From the point of view of individual interests, it

is desirable to give more preference to profitability criteria, but this inevitably undermines the balance in environmental protection, in nature protection. Consequently, the work to be done in order to obtain acceptable forecasts requires the early development of criteria for socio-economic assessments that are correct from the point of view of the welfare of society. The application of such criteria increases the importance of forecasting structural changes taking place in the Azerbaijan economy, and at the same time requires clarification, grouping and improvement of issues embedded in several existing methodological indicators and forecasting methods.

In recent years, as in economically developed countries, in the countries of the Republic of Azerbaijan, special attention has been paid to forecasting, which is an integral part of socio-economic management. Since long-term planning in the EP Environment Protection areas is pre-determined for 15 years, the useful life of the forecast that forms the basis of this planning should not be less than 20 years.

In our opinion, the structure of the sector forecast units can be presented in the form of Table 1.

Forecasting is carried out on three levels: a) the first one is for individual enterprises and industrial associations (forecast of environmental impact); b) the second one is for a specific region (a comprehensive forecast and assessment of expected results reflecting changes in environmental quality); c) the third is in the industry as a whole (summary forecast).

According to the structure of the proposed ecological and economic forecasting, it is advisable to classify the methodology of forecasting the technical impact in the field of EOS on the basis of two basic principles: to determine the scale of interaction with the environment; to study the quality of the environment. At the same time, the statistical method can be used to predict the degree of impact of territories on the environment. However, it should be noted that it is not always possible to use statistical methods to determine changes in environmental quality. For this reason, we believe that the most effective methods in the current situation are cartography, geophysics, experiments and combined methods. The statistical method should be applied only to selected indicators with initial data.

Table 1.

Structure of industry forecasting issues in the oil and gas industry *

Scientific and technical section of the forecast	Socio-economic section of the forecast
- analysis of the ecological situation at the locations of field facilities and study of factors affecting the EPA;	- forecast of economic losses, depending on the nature protection options;
- study of the impact on the nature protection activities of STP at the predicted time;	- calculation of socio-economic assessment of the results of each option;
- environmental pollution and the amount of pollution, the development of forecasts for changes in regulatory frameworks, changes in the composition and structure of toxic components;	- determination of the efficiency of nature protection measures and selection of a suitable option;
- characteristics of alternative variants of nature protection measures, the volume of capital investments and operating costs;	- proposals and recommendations for the formation of a plan of nature protection measures that provide long-term goals and standards;
- characteristics of alternative options of nature protection measures, volume of relevant capital investments and operating costs;	

* compiled by the author on the basis of [11]

To predict the expected socio-economic results, it is advisable to use a balance method, an economic and mathematical model, a survey method and a combined method. It is advisable to use the regulatory option to study the protection of the environmental quality standard and factors affecting the environment in a regulatory situation; the main purpose of using the intermediate forecast option is to study the degree of environmental impact of territories where a certain level of environmental protection measures is in effect.

Based on the above, the following key points can be noted when developing the scientific and technical part of the forecast: a) analysis of the current environmental situation; b) forecast of the scale of the object's impact on the environment and nature protection [20-23].

However, it should be noted that in order to implement the above measures, some changes are needed (consideration of several variants of forecasts, the use of more effective forecasting methods, improvement of the forecasting system). At the same time, the analysis of the environmental situation as the initial stage of the forecast development is the basis for further research.

Increased demand for carbon-intensive energy as a result of population and income growth leads to an increase in IEW emissions in general (Table 2).

The forecast data depends primarily on a comprehensive and accurate analysis of the state of the environment. The main purpose of the analysis is to collect, process and systematize the initial data necessary for making a forecast.

The following questions should be taken into account in the analysis: 1) identification of factors affecting the environment at the facilities of the oil and gas industry; 2) determination of the scale and type of impact; 3) detection of trends and qualitative changes in the activity of the natural environment; 4) study of the scale of damage caused by objects of the oil and gas industry; 5) identification of a situation that may create an environmental threat in the region.

The data obtained for analysis should be based on field statistics and monitoring system data. Currently, the wells are in the process of creating a field control system in the most dangerous areas. The main issues of forecasting changes in the quality of EPC under the influence of oil and gas industry enterprises are: 1) identification of pollution zones and qualitative changes in the environment due to toxic concentrations; 2) determining the degree of quality deviation in the EPA compared to the regulatory situation; 3) identification of the crisis zone of the natural system.

Table 2.

IEYQ Waste sources, Azerbaijan ("No action taken" scenario, 100th year GWPs) *

Sector	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Transport	2.2	4.2	5.0	6.6	7.0	7.7	8.4	9.2	9.9	10.7	11.6
Industry	6.4	2.8	1.6	1.4	1.0	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.6
Place of residence	3.7	6.6	6.5	6.4	7.3	8.3	9.4	10.6	11.9	13.3	14.9
Commercial	0.8	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	0.3	0.8	1.1	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.6	0.5
Electricity	11.0	14.1	10.5	10.3	10.3	10.2	10.2	10.4	10.7	10.3	11.6
Gas Production	4.7	5.1	11.7	12.1	12.3	12.6	13.0	13.2	14.2	14.7	15.9
Other power supply	4.2	5.6	4.3	5.4	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.2	5.3	5.3	5.4
Industrial processes	0.6	1.8	2.1	2.8	3.2	3.8	4.4	5.2	6.1	7.2	8.4
Agriculture	5.4	6.5	7.2	8.5	9.5	10.5	11.5	12.5	13.5	14.5	15.5
Land Use and Forestry	-4.9	-5.3	-5.4	-5.5	-5.5	-5.5	-5.5	-5.5	-5.5	-5.5	-5.5
Waste	1.8	2.0	2.3	2.4	2.6	2.7	2.9	3.1	3.3	3.5	3.7

* compiled by the author on the basis of [24]

The most effective method for predicting EPA quality variability is the cartography method. The map is a visual aid on topography, zones and directions of environmental pollution. The cartographic model allows you to select suitable sites for the placement and development of an object, while prohibiting the placement of new industrial facilities in certain territories or suspending or significantly limiting the operation of existing ones. Experiments show that the cartographic method is more reliable because it is tracked using environmental maps compiled in the UK. In Germany, these maps are used to determine the level of air pollution with sulfur dioxide. The main difficulty when using the mapping method is calculating the concentration level in accordance with the concentration. However, a number of proposals, guidelines and geophysical models have been written and published in this area [25]. However, these substances make it possible to more accurately determine the degree of air pollution.

When choosing a method for determining economic damage, the possibilities and goals of a specific forecast should be taken into account. It should be noted that to determine the local damage separately, calculations are required for each damage. For example, when determining the damage (Y_d) caused by the deterioration of public health, three of its main components are taken into account: non-labor national income as a result of refusal to work (Q_n y/week) Q_n/g w for health reasons; payment of benefits to persons with temporary disability (Q_{ab} w); medical expenses of the patient (Q_{m.c}):

$$(Q_{m.c})(Q_{m.c})Y_d = Q_n/g w + Q_{ab} w + Q_{m.c} \quad (1)$$

Production losses are due to an increase in the depreciation rate of certain fixed assets (A_f); valuable raw material wastes released into the atmosphere (A_{rw}); losses incurred during high employee turnover are calculated (A).

$$A_s = A_f + A_{rw} + A \quad (2)$$

When calculating the damage to housing and communal services (H_{Cs}) from air pollution, the following is taken into account: the cost of cleaning the additional dust generated in the areas allocated for construction in the city (H_{Cl}) public transport ($H_{p,t}$) value-added expenditures of housing funds and other objects of the city (H_{cost}) additional costs of household services (H_h); damage to urban landscaping (H_d)

$$D_h = H_{Cl} + H_{p,t} + H_{cost} + H_h + H_d \quad (3)$$

In order to use the method described above to determine economic losses, it is necessary to collect, analyze and summarize a large amount of information according to this scheme, the complexity of obtaining such information is due to their nature. It should be pointed out that it is impossible to obtain the necessary data in a generalized form, since there is no single body in Azerbaijan that would deal with this. Moreover, there are problems with the collection of primary data, since it is impossible to obtain the necessary information for all enterprises. In the future, the calculations will use the data of

SOCAR, the state oil company of Azerbaijan, the largest in the republic.

The method of calculating the specific gravity of damage is given below. For example, the economic damage from concentrates is determined by the following formula.

$$D = \sum_i Z_i R_i + D_a/culture R_i + D_e \cdot S_i + D_{in,i} F_i \quad (4)$$

$D_{h/I}$ – i specific gravity of health damage in the zone;

R_i – i number of populations living in the zone;

$D_a/culture$ – i specific weight of damage to forestry;

S_i – i zone suitable forest areas;

D_e – i zone specific gravity of damage to the environment;

$D_{in,i}$ – i zone specific gravity of damage to the industry;

F_i – i the value of the main funds of the industry.

Thus, when calculating economic damage by this method, differentiation of pollution levels in zones requires the collection of a large amount of preliminary data. Accordingly, it can be said that the existing scientific and methodological work does not allow taking into account the indicators characterizing economic damage when planning and forecasting the gas industry in the field of EOS.

To predict the economic damage from air pollution using an extended assessment method, the following indicators should be taken into account:

- 1) the volume, composition and composition of toxic substances released into the atmosphere;
- 2) changing the nature of pollution;
- 3) forecasting of economic damage.

Azerbaijan's transition to a market economy is accompanied by high activity in the development of the oil and gas sector, but the severity of the economic crisis has led to a deterioration in the quality of the environment and, as a result, the deterioration of the health of the population in crisis conditions, a decrease in life expectancy and other adverse demographic consequences. Thus, there is a great need to create a new state

environmental policy aimed at ensuring rational use of natural resources, improving the state of the environment and reducing the negative impact on human health, without which sustainable development and stability of society as a whole is impossible. The concept of "sustainable development" for the "society-environment" system should be understood as follows:

- sustainable social development, involving the use of sources to ensure equality of community members and create conditions for social justice;

- ecological sustainable development, in which human well-being is ensured by the protection of natural well-being and the quality of the environment.

According to the World Bank, sustainable development means achieving the following goals [26]: environmental degradation, biodiversity diversity, protection of favorable environmental conditions, etc. [27; 28]; environmental goals; simple economic goals that ensure the development and efficiency of the economy; social goals [29].

However, achieving one of the above goals contradicts the realization of social goals with an increase in production in the economy, or rather, there is a contradiction between environmental and economic goals. Taken into account the sustainability of economic and social development and its compliance with environmental requirements, it is necessary to understand the main problem – the importance of minimizing negative environmental consequences for future generations. And in order to determine the specific goals of this development and to take into account the long-term environmental consequences of any enterprise (economy) affected by pollution and environmental degradation, people's economic activity can be considered the primary and most important element of this process. To minimize such negative impacts, it is necessary to develop a strategy (from the point of view of restoring quality) that ensures that the economy meets the environmental requirements of measures aimed at reducing the burden on the environment. Adoption as a technological, financial and economic measure supports the goal of production – the necessary income, according to experts, four types of strategies can be applied. The first strategy is based on the fact that when calculating the effectiveness of any production or trade operation, it is necessary to take into account the economic damage caused by environmental pollution as a result of this operation.

The second strategy should be to minimize the amount of waste in technological processes through regenerative measures. The third strategy is aimed at reducing environmental risk and can be applied at enterprises that have reliable environmental protection measures, but use highly toxic and radioactive materials in their production. The fourth strategy is aimed at minimizing the overall impact of the enterprise on the environment. When implementing this strategy, the company can apply more radical changes in its production and trading activities, for example, the cessation of production of certain types of products. The choice of a particular type of strategy is based on the analysis of the following parameters:

- the general environmental situation in the region;

- production capabilities (enterprises);
- the level of availability of environmental protection equipment in production activities;
- financial stability of the enterprise;
- innovative activity in the implementation of the medium- and long-term strategy of the enterprise and the policy of restoration of production.

As part of the expansion of the level of economic activity to adapt to environmental requirements, much attention should be paid to environmental monitoring and environmental expertise (verification and assessment of compliance of economic activities with environmental protection requirements).

Every country, including Azerbaijan, contributes to the global environmental crisis. Such a contribution can be assessed by ecological significance, the size of territories in which natural ecosystems are disturbed or not disturbed, as well as by the consumption of primary pure biota (flora and fauna) in each other and in each country. The current environmental situation has forced each country to consider environmental problems in a global context [30-32].

According to international experts, natural gas coming from Turkmenistan to Nakhchivan, via Iran, can further expand the capacity of SGC in Turkey in the future [35]. As well as the implementation of the Trans-Caspian Gas Pipeline project (Trans-Caspian Gas Pipeline, "TCGP") will allow the Central Asian countries to supply gas to the countries of the continent in the amount of an additional 10-12 billion cubic meters per year through the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan and Turkey. According to many experts, Caspian gas supplies can pass through the TANAP and TAP gas pipelines, and the countries of the region can increase their importance in the global economy and receive additional profits [35]. The production and supply of liquefied natural gas (LNG) also has good prospects, is a politically and economically profitable direction.

Conclusions

The article proposes directions for forecasting environmental problems caused by oil and gas industry.

Based on the analysis, a number of important results have been achieved in the protection of nature and the environment, and it is recommended to implement measures that include:

1. Apply an effective implementation mechanism that combines the types of economic and administrative impact. First of all, it is about environmental safety measures at enterprises.
2. Improving the environmental literacy of the population and oil and gas companies. The most successful method of achieving this is the introduction of seminars – advanced training courses for specialists of the oil and gas industrial complex.
3. Increasing the number of environmental measures. The state should play an important role in this.
4. Rational use of non-renewable energy sources and expansion of the use of renewable energy sources.
5. Development of the non-oil sector in order to reduce the use of oil. Again, we are talking about renewable energy sources.
6. Strengthen the process of recultivation of

polluted lands. Local self-government bodies and territorial communities are able to ensure this, therefore it is recommended to give them greater powers to solve this task.

7. Strengthen the material and technical base of oil and gas producing enterprises with new equipment and technologies. Establishment and development of cooperation with foreign partners is of great importance here.

Thus, on the one hand, the development of the oil and gas industry contributes to the economic well-being of the state, on the other hand, it generates more and more environmental problems. This is a well-known global model of economic development, which is aimed at short-term interests, unlimited growth and consumption of natural resources. We recommend thinking about the future and implementing strategically important measures, in particular switching to renewable energy sources.

Regarding the operating oil and gas complex, effective management of strategic as well as specific risks should be based on comprehensive identification and description of risks, as well as identification of key indicators of the oil and gas industry, which will allow in practice to comprehensively take into account both the negative consequences of the event and the positive ones. Additionally, in order to minimize political and economic risks, to ensure uninterrupted and reliable export of natural gas from Azerbaijan to the countries of the continent, it is advisable to have alternative routes for transporting natural gas, taking into account the risk of the transit country.

References

1. Suleymanov G S and Turkan Sh A 2020 Enhancing the efficiency of environmental and economic risks management for oil and gas producing enterprises in Azerbaijan Scientific Bulletin of IFNTUOG Series: Economics and Management in the Oil and Gas Industry 2 22 7-17
2. Feizullaev A A, Kocharli S S and Abbasova S V 2020 Oil and Gas Potential of Superimposed Depressions in Azerbaijan Gornye nauki i tehnologii – Mining Science and Technology. 20205 2 72-81
3. Azerbaijan State Statistics Committee <https://www.stat.gov.az> 2022 Accessed 15 Oct 2022
4. Gershtansky O S 2016 Topical issues of the oil and gas industry (Aktau: JSC NIPIneftegaz)
5. Hajiyeva M 2015 Ecology and environmental protection Voice July 7 p 12
6. Goldfein M D, Kozhevnikov N V and Kozhevnikova N I 2006 Fundamentals of ecology, life safety and economic and legal regulation of environmental management (Moscow: Publishing house of RGTEU)
7. Use of Gravity and Magnetic Methods in Oil and Gas Exploration: Case Studies from Azerbaijan https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356596315_Use_of_Gravity_and_Magnetic_Methods_in_Oil_and_Gas_Exploration_Case_Studies_from_Azerbaijan2022 Accessed 15 Oct 2022
8. Alieva L 2009 The Center for National and International Studies (Baku: Qanun)

9. Gravity-magnetic survey for the oil and gas prospecting in Azerbaijan and Ukraine https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315371073_Gravity-magnetic_survey_for_the_oil_and_gas_prospecting_in_Azerbaijan_and_Ukraine 2022 Accessed 15 Oct 2022
10. Huseynzade R and Aliyev A 2016 Experience of Azerbaijan in construction of main oil and gas pipelines in the Caspian Sea Region. Environmental aspects, Oil and gas pipelines in the Black-Caspian Seas Region eds I S Zonn and A G Kostianoy (Switzerland: Springer)
11. Nuraliyeva R N 2010 Economic and ecological problems of development of fuel and energy complex of Azerbaijan (Baku: AZ)
12. State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Oil and Ecology www.gia.az 2022 Accessed 4 June 2022
13. Mukhsinova L H 2003 Efficient use of electricity in Azerbaijan in market conditions Proceedings of the NAS Institute of Economics Baku 479-491
14. State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan www.socar.az 2022 Accessed 5 June 2022
15. Enerji Products Report <http://www.worldoil.com> 2022 Accessed 4 June 2022
16. Global Energy Statistical Yearbook 2019 <https://www.enerdata.net/about-us/company-news/energy-statistical-yearbook-updated.html> 2022 Accessed 1 June 2022
17. World Energy Outlook 2015 <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2015> 2016 Accessed 1 June 2022
18. Ministry of Industry and Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan www.mie.gov.az 2022 Accessed 5 June 2022
19. BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2018 (UK: Pureprint Group Limited)
20. Tetelmin B V and Yazev V A 2009 Environmental protection in the oil and gas complex Dolgoprudny Publishing House Intellect 352 p
21. Kallis G, Kerschner C and Martinez-Alier J 2012 The economics of edgrowth Ecological Economics 2012 84 172-180
22. Ibrahimov I H 2015 Economy of the environment Baku 357 p
23. Guliyeva Kh B 2015 Methods for determining the economic indicators of damage caused by environmental pollution Geography: theory, practice and innovations 12 614-621
24. World Institute for Environmental Monitoring www.coe.int 2022 Accessed 1 June 2022
25. International Organization for Standardization ISO 14004:1996 Environmental Management Systems General Guidelines on Principles, Systems and Supporting Techniques 1996 Geneva ISO
26. World Bank Group Climate Change Action Plan 2021-2025 www.worldbank.org 2020 Accessed 1 June 2022
27. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on nature protection and use of nature <http://www.e-qanun.az> 2022 Accessed 3 June 2022
28. Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan https://www.azerbaijans.com/content_516_eng.html 2022 Accessed 3 June 2022
29. Report on Social Protection in the World 2017-2019 www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/ 2020 Accessed 5 June 2022
30. Azerbaijan 2020: Vision for the Future Development Concept Approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan December 29 2012
31. BP-Azərbaycan. Report www.bp.com 2022 Accessed 1 June 2022
32. US Institute of International Economics www.iie.com 2022 Accessed 1 June 2022
33. Karataev A S and Shumilova V M 2012 Specific risks are generators of financial risks typical for oil and gas companies Bulletin of the Ugra State University 4 27 41-44.
34. Benashvili K A 2020 The role of the Southern Gas Corridor project in the implementation of the European Union's energy strategy. Creative Economics 9-14 2181-2193
35. Interview of İlham Aliyev to Azerbaijan Television <https://president.az/ru/articles/view/55989> 2021 Accessed 5 June 2022